

A Hybrid Approach to Address IP Traceback Problem using Nature Inspired Algorithm

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Abstract— Internet has always been vulnerable to security threats. With the growth in usage of Internet, rate of cyber crime has also increased tremendously. Out of number of possible attacks, the most precarious is Denial of Service (DoS) attack. It provides the attacker an opportunity to use the vulnerabilities of a large number of compromised hosts in a network and create attack networks or Botnets. These compromised systems usually disguise their identity by falsifying the source address in Internet Protocol (IP) header known as address spoofing. Further the stateless nature of IP makes the situation perilous. The best possible way to deal with DoS attacks is to find the source of attack. IP Traceback is a proactive and effective approach to detect the origin of the DoS attack and mitigating it with the cooperation of ISP's. This approach helps in restoring routine network traffic, prevents any chances of future attacks and brings the attacker responsible for attack in front of law. The origin once detected can be blocked for further attacks and the traceback information collected helps in mitigation process. The process of backtracking for finding an anonymous attacker on a vast network is a quite complex and challenging problem. In this paper, we have proposed a hybrid IP Traceback approach. Instead of processing large volume of data generated for traceback or modifying the network components, the proposed approach is based on utilizing flow level information to detect source of DoS attack.

The proposed hybrid approach is based on two nature inspired algorithms, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), which have proved to be the most effective approaches in solving combinatorial optimization problems. The main focus of this work is to improve the convergence rate and reduce the computational complexity of Ant Colony Optimization algorithm, which performs search operation on the basis of distance by combining it with particle velocity based technique called Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm. The objective behind is to avoid premature convergence and obtain fast convergence with lesser number of ants in solving IP traceback problem.

The proposed method is evaluated through simulating it on Network Simulator 2 and the results show that the method can successfully and efficiently detects the DoS attack path with reduced convergence time and computational complexity.

Keywords— DoS; TCP/IP; ICMP; ACO; PSO;

I. INTRODUCTION

Denial of Service (DoS) poses a severe threat to Internet by preventing the authorized users from accessing the services and resources from network. DoS attacks are common due to stateless nature of TCP/IP protocol suite in which packets are

routed without source address verification. Thus, IP address in attack packets is generally spoofed to implement a DoS attack [1][2][3]. A DoS attack can reduce victim's ability to respond to the legitimate user by making victim's resources unavailable for some time or ceasing them permanently by flooding huge traffic thus depleting victim's bandwidth and processing power or both [4]. According to a study conducted in 2012 by a security and data protection research institute, Ponemon Institute, "The average amount of downtime following a DDoS attack is 54 minutes and the average cost for each minute of downtime was about \$22,000. However, the cost can range from as little as \$1 to more than \$100,000 per minute of downtime." [5] Many organizations use a combination of firewalls and intrusion detection system (IDS) to secure their network. IDS detect the malicious traffic and coordinate with firewalls to block it. Most of the work done in this area focused on pacifying the effect of attack by sustaining it to certain extent. Also these techniques fail in case if falsified or spoofed IP addresses are used to launch these attacks. Such passive approaches can provide only provisional solution, which neither eradicates the root cause of the problem nor captures and produces the attacker in front of law. The best way to deal with such attacks is not only to prevent them but also finding the origin of attack to mitigate it in least possible time and holding the attacker.

One such proactive approach is IP-Traceback, which is the scheme of finding the origin of attack. It is used to detect the attack path or the path followed by attack packets. Attack path may consist of a number of routers within a domain or between different domains as Internet services are provided by various Internet Service Providers (ISP). Traceback is not a preventive measure, which is adopted before the commencement of attack, it begins only after the attack has actually started. Also Traceback is quite beneficial in post-attack analysis and we can block the attack origin to mitigate future possible attacks. The major challenges in IP-Traceback are segregating attack packets from legitimate packets and finding attackers identity with spoofed IP address packets.

The conventional IP-Traceback schemes require alteration of various network components. Either specific fields of the IP header of a packet are used to store router's information in encoded form or certain amount of the packet describing factors are stored at the routers for the purpose of IP traceback. Also, the schemes require all the routers in network

to support traceback mechanism [6]. V. A. Foroushani, et al. [7] described and implemented probabilistic packet marking (PPM) for performing IP-Traceback. The path information in the form of fingerprint is embedded in the packets randomly according to some predefined probability, which helps in detecting the origin of attack. J. Liu, et al. [8] implemented dynamic probabilistic packet marking (DPPM) technique by using distance travelled by packets as a parameter for marking probability instead of using fixed probabilities which results into better performance. S. Yu, et al. [9] implemented traceback by using dynamic deterministic packet marking (DDPM) where instead of marking all the nodes only the nodes involved in attack like ingress routers are marked and used to detect the attack source. S. Saurabh and A. Sairam [10] performed Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) based IP-Traceback also known as iTrace schemes. They have considered the main problem with these schemes, that is huge traffic generated by ICMP packets and they proposed a system of two bloom filters known as Additive and Multiplicative Bloom Filters, which when incorporated with reverse iTrace reduces the number of iTrace generated approximately by 100 times. Thus it prevents iTrace from becoming another DoS attack during the reflector attack. H. Aljifri, et al. [11] proposed a novel approach using header compression for traceback. Header compression results in storing more information in the packet without affecting its size and hence proves to be an effective PPM technique for IP-Traceback. Y. Fen, et al. [12] proposed IP-Traceback by using time to live (TTL) field of IP header. The information generated by TTL is used to generate attack path thus no additional information needs to be incorporated in the IP packets.

These traditional traceback approaches need a lot of changes in infrastructure and put a lot of computational load on routers. Also they require high memory capacity in routers and consume a lot of network bandwidth in carrying traceback information. A new way to deal with IP traceback problem is the use of meta heuristic techniques. Meta heuristic is a heuristic or procedure designed to generate an optimal solution to an optimization problem, especially when complete information is not available or computation capacity is limited. Meta heuristic are capable of generating a sample out of large sample space and makes a few assumptions to solve a wide variety of optimization problems.

Traditional techniques like optimization algorithm and iterative methods guarantee a globally optimum solution but its not so in case of meta heuristic algorithms. Meta heuristics make use of stochastic optimization techniques to find a solution, which is dependent on the set of random variables. This technique proves to be a better choice involving less computational effort in solving combinatorial optimization problems, over a set of large feasible solutions, as compared to simple heuristics, iterative methods or other optimization algorithms. Since IP Traceback is a combinatorial optimization problem, which falls under NP-hard category, a meta heuristic approach can provide better and fast solution as compared to traditional techniques. The goal of this work is to propose an IP-Traceback approach, which uses a hybrid of two meta heuristic algorithms and

existing flow information to determine the attack origin. The proposed scheme hybridizes Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) into PSO-ACO to minimize the number of routing packets required and the time required to converge to the most probable attack path.

II. RELATED WORK

G. H. Lai, et al. [13] have proposed traceback approach based on Ant algorithm to find out the source of DoS attack. The algorithm is inspired by food collecting behavior of ants. In an ant algorithm, all the ants (agents) cooperate with each other by exchanging necessary information in the form of stored pheromone, a chemical substance released by ants. Ants mark the path they traverse by laying pheromone in certain quantity according to the priority of the path. Rest of the ants follow the path according to a certain probability depending on the quantity of pheromone laid by ants. A single ant algorithm converges very fast but results in a bad optimal solution. When multiple ants interact with each other the algorithm converges to a sub-space of many good solutions out of which the best solution can be selected as the final solution [6]. The proposed traceback approach does not require processing of large amount of data or creating new type of functions to find the attack source rather it works on flow level information to perform traceback operation. The approach overpowers traditional approaches by possessing two features, quick convergence and heuristics, which help in reaching the attack source quickly. The performance of approach was successfully evaluated on two simulated networks, NSFNET and DFN.

M. H. Hamzehkolaie, et al. [14] have proposed a bee colony algorithm for detecting the DoS attack source. They used the quick convergence and heuristics to find the source of DoS attack. The food source exploring nature of bees form the basis of solution to traceback problem. The traffic flow information serves as a food source for bees. The path with more traffic is more prone to fall under DoS affected path. Simulation results prove the efficiency of algorithm. The technique proves to be efficient as it do not require much storage, also it do not demand any changes in the routing infrastructure.

P. Wang, et al. [15] have proposed an improved Ant colony algorithm for IP Traceback problem. The algorithm focuses on improving the ability of ants to converge to attack path by implementing Ant colony algorithm on smaller subgroups where each subgroup has its own pheromone update rule. Though the algorithm converges slower than conventional Ant colony algorithm but it uses a local update rule along with the global update rule to update the path information of moving ants which generates a more globally optimum path.

III. INTRODUCTION TO PSO AND ACO

A. Particle Swarm Optimization

Particle Swarm Optimization is a meta-heuristic technique proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart [16] based on natural behavior of swarm of birds. Initially it generates a set of random solutions and with each generation it upgrades the

solution till optimum solution is reached. Each particle in PSO has a position and a velocity and it keeps the memory of its previous best position, p_{best} , and the best position attained by all the particles in swarm called g_{best} . Every move of particle is governed by the values of p_{best} and g_{best} . [17]. Each particle first moves toward local optimum solution and converges with each generation.

PSO algorithm optimizes the values of p_{best} and g_{best} using a fitness function. The velocity of particle is updated according to Eq. (1).

$$V_{new} = w \times V_{old} + c_1 \times r_1 \times (p_{best} - P_{old}) + c_2 \times r_2 \times (g_{best} - P_{old}) \quad (1)$$

Here P_{old} and V_{old} are the position and velocity of particle in previous iterations. V_{new} is the new value of velocity calculated for present iteration. c_1, c_2 are learning factors lying between [0,1]. r_1, r_2 are random numbers lying in range (0,1) to restrict the rise in value of velocity to a certain permissible level and w denotes the weight or inertia factor.

After updating velocity each particle updates its position according to the equation Eq. (2).

$$P_{new} = V_{new} + P_{old} \quad (2)$$

Particles updates their velocity and position till the termination conditions are met. The algorithm describing basic steps of PSO is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1. Steps of Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm

- Initialize position of particles randomly;
- Initialize velocity of particles based on fitness function;
- Repeat
- Calculate local best and global best solution i.e p_{best} and g_{best} ;
- Update velocity of each particle according to Eq. (1);
- Update position of each particle according to Eq. (2);
- Until termination condition is met or number of iterations are over;
- Final value of g_{best} gives the solution;

B. Ant Colony Optimization

In ACO algorithm proposed by M. Dorigo, et al. [6], all the ants (agents) cooperate with each other by exchanging necessary information in the form of stored pheromone, a chemical substance released by ants to find shortest path to food source from their home. Ants mark the path they traverse by laying pheromone in varying quantity depending on the distance of the path and the food quality. Also certain amount of pheromone evaporates with time. Each ant selects its next move to an edge depending on pheromone concentration and heuristic value of that edge.

In Ant based IP-Traceback each ant remembers the value of fitness function, which is the best position attained by it. A distance metric storing the path lengths of all routers and a probability metric based on flow information and pheromone value of each path are maintained according to Eq. (3). Each ant makes a move depending on the values of distance and probability metrics and updates the value of pheromone

deposited on the path traversed by it according to Eq. (4). The algorithm runs till all the ants converge to a single path.

$$p_{ij}(t) = \frac{[\tau_{ij}(t)]^\alpha [\eta_{ij}(t)]^\beta}{\sum_{j \in N_i} [\tau_{ij}(t)]^\alpha [\eta_{ij}(t)]^\beta} \quad (3)$$

Here $p_{ij}(t)$ is the probability of ant choosing a path from node i to node j . τ_{ij} is the pheromone concentration on the edge between nodes i and j .

$$\eta_{ij}(t) = \frac{1}{d_{ij}}, \text{ where } d_{ij} \text{ is the distance between node } i \text{ and } j.$$

α and β are decay factors representing the fading value of pheromone with time. The value of pheromone is updated according to Eq. (4).

$$\tau_{ij}(t + 1) = (1 - \rho) \tau_{ij}(t) + \Delta \tau_{ij}(t) \quad (4)$$

Here ρ represents pheromone decay rate and its value lies in the interval [0,1] and $\Delta \tau_{ij}(t)$ represents additional pheromone deposited over the time period t calculated as shown in Eq. (5).

$$\Delta \tau_{ij}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^m \tau_{ij}(k) \quad (5)$$

The algorithm describing basic steps of ACO is shown in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2. Steps of Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm

- Assign value of initial solution to each ant;
- Initialize value of pheromone trail;
- Repeat for all ants
- Construct distance metric based on flow information and path length;
- Construct probability metric according to Eq. (3);
- Use local search to decide move of each ant on the basis of metrics;
- Update the pheromone concentration according to Eq. (4);
- Until stopping condition is met or edge router is reached;

The algorithm overpowers traditional approaches by possessing two features, quick convergence and heuristics, which help in reaching the attack source quickly. Quick convergence is helpful in identifying the source of a DoS attack and heuristic generates the solution even with limited traffic information. Though the algorithm suffers from the problem of convergence to local optimal solution.

C. Hybrid PSO-ACO Algorithm

The proposed hybrid algorithm integrates the distance-based search of ACO with velocity-based search of PSO to design a new meta heuristic approach which improves the performance of ACO algorithm in solving IP-Traceback problem. Both ACO and PSO suffer from the problem of convergence to local optimum due to unrealistic initialization of pheromone concentration in ACO and distance of particles in case of PSO. In ACO every move of ant is decided according to its previous best move so local update is there. In PSO-ACO the position of each ant is updated on the basis of local as well as global best value of fitness function resulting into faster convergence and a more globally optimum solution. Also PSO-ACO converges to attack path with lesser number of ants thus we can say that computational complexity of hybrid algorithm is less as compared to ACO algorithm.

The velocity and position of particles in PSO-ACO algorithm is calculated according to Eq. (6) and Eq. (7). Three weight factors Ψ_e, Ψ_c, Ψ_s are used in calculating the velocity of particle. Out of these Ψ_e, Ψ_c are dependent on PSO cost function. But Ψ_s depend on ACO cost function and it is used as accelerator for PSO-ACO optimization.

$$V_{i,d}^k(t+1) = \Psi_e \times r_e \times V_{i,d}^k(t) + \Psi_c \times r_c \times (P_c - X_{i,d}^k(t)) + \Psi_s \times r_s \times (P_s - X_{i,d}^k(t)) \quad (6)$$

$$X_{i,d}^k(t+1) = X_{i,d}^k(t) + V_{i,d}^k(t+1) \quad (7)$$

Here P_c and P_s are local and global best position values and $X_{i,d}^k(t), V_{i,d}^k(t)$ are the position and velocity of ant k at time t on edge (i, d).

Eq. (8), (9) and (10) are used in optimization process when position of minima is stuck in false minima. So it is needed to converge the path by ACO functionality, for that Eq. (8) changes the particle pheromones by (ρ) and $(1-\rho)$. ρ represents the learning parameter, which decides that how much part of the previous learning is use for next prediction.

$$J_{ij}^k(t+1) = \rho \times (J_{ij}^k(t) + T_{ij}^k) - (1-\rho) \times e \times J_{ij}^k(t) \quad (8)$$

where $0 < \rho < 1, 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, e < 1$ and T_{ij}^k is a function whose value is

$$T_{ij} = \begin{cases} \alpha, & \text{if source is pheromone} \\ \beta, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The learning factor R is used to calculate the fitness function according to Eq. (9).

$$\mu_{ij}^k(t) = \frac{(k_1 \times W_{ij}^k(t) - k_2 \times J_{ij}^k(t))}{R} \quad (9)$$

Here $\mu_{ij}^k(t)$ denote the target utility of agent k and $W_{ij}^k(t)$ and $J_{ij}^k(t)$ denotes the path weight and pheromone intensity respectively.

Amount or concentration of pheromone on each path is calculated as per Eq. (10).

$$\eta_{ij}^k(t) = \Omega^k / d_{is}^k(t) \quad (10)$$

If value of $\eta_{ij}^k(t) > 1$ then set $\eta_{ij}^k(t) = 1$. Ω^k is the local detection factor based on flow information and $d_{is}^k(t)$ is the distance between the ant k and the attack source.

The hybrid PSO-ACO algorithm is shown in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3. Basic steps of PSO-ACO algorithm.

At $t=0$, initialize N ant agents in 2D space;
 Set the value of $\{P_{ij}\}^k = \{\}$;
 For $k=1$ to N
 Set the value of $\psi_c = \psi_s = 0$;
 Calculate $V_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (6);
 Calculate $P_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (7);
 End For
 While (stopping condition not met)
 For $k= 1$ to N
 do
 If (attack source not detected) and (no pheromone received)
 Set the value of $\psi_e \neq 0$;
 Set the value of $\psi_c = 0$;

Set the value of $\psi_s = 0$;
 Calculate $V_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (6);
 Calculate $P_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (7);
 Else if (source is detected)
 Set the value of $\psi_e = 0$;
 Set the value of $\psi_c \neq 0$;
 Set the value of $\psi_s = 0$;
 Calculate $V_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (6);
 Calculate $P_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (7);
 Else if (Pheromone(s) is received)
 Update the value of $\{P_{ij}\}^k$;
 For $m = 1$ to size $\{P_{ij}\}^k$
 Find J_{ij}^k using Eq. (8);
 Find μ_{ij}^k using Eq. (9);
 Find η_{ij}^k using Eq. (10);
 If $\eta_{ij}^k > 1$ then set $\eta_{ij}^k = 1$;
 End for
 Set the value of $\psi_e \neq 0$;
 Set the value of $\psi_c \neq 0$;
 Set the value of $\psi_s \neq 0$;
 Calculate $V_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (6);
 Calculate $P_{i,d}^k(t+1)$ using Eq. (7);
 End for

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

Both the ACO algorithm and PSO-ACO algorithm were simulated on Network Simulator2 (NS2). The simulation scenario used with ten number of nodes is displayed in Fig. 1. It simulates four legitimate traffic flows in the network and DoS attack flow through the routers 1, 3, 5, 6, 8 and 9. The results of simulation are displayed in Figs. 2-3. Fig. 2. show that PSO-ACO takes lesser number of iterations to converge to DoS attack path. Hence PSO-ACO algorithm converges to attack path faster than ACO so its convergence rate is improved over ACO algorithm. The path 3,5,6,8,9,1, which is the DoS attack path, is followed by maximum number of ants as shown in Fig. 3. The number of ants used to detect attack path, is found to be less in case of PSO-ACO as compared to ACO as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. Network Scenario used for Simulation

So, the computational complexity of PSO-ACO algorithm, which is directly proportional to the number of ants used to detect attack path, is less as compared to ACO algorithm.

Thus, hybrid algorithm has better convergence rate and less computational complexity over ACO algorithm.

Fig. 2. Comparison of convergence rate of ACO with PSO-ACO

Fig. 3. DoS attack path detected with different number of ants by both algorithm

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed a hybrid algorithm integrates the concept of distance metric from ACO and direction or velocity metric from PSO to compute a new probability metric thereby resulting into finding a more globally optimum solution for IP Traceback problem with improved convergence rate. Both ACO and PSO suffer from the problem of convergence to local suboptimal solution. Initial movement of ants in ACO is governed by the initial concentration of pheromone on paths, which has a great impact on overall convergence of the algorithm. If more pheromone is there on sub-optimal paths then the algorithm gets trapped into local optima. To overcome this problem a large number of ants are needed thereby increasing the convergence time of algorithm. In PSO also initial position of particles is fixed randomly and the

convergence of algorithm highly depends on these values. Random selection of position may sometimes result into a bad sub-optimal solution. Thus the proposed hybrid algorithm integrates the local update information obtained from distance metric of ACO with the global update information obtained from velocity metric of PSO (based on pbest and gbest) and selects a more reliable path with the help of new probability metric based on local as well as global information. Simulation results shows that the proposed algorithm outperforms ant based traceback in terms of convergence rate and it successfully generates a more globally optimum solution. We have also observed that the proposed algorithm converges to attack path in lesser number of iterations and with less number of particles or ants. From observations, we believe that the proposed hybrid approach is an effective way of finding optimal solution to traceback problem.

As a future work, methods could be devised to further improve the convergence rate of algorithm especially in case of larger networks and in more practical conditions. In large search space convergence to local optima is another major challenge, which could be looked upon as future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Patel and V. Jha, "Various anti IP spoofing techniques," *Journal of Engineering Computers & Applied Sciences*, Vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 27-31, 2015.
- [2] N. Gupta and M. Dhiman, "A study of DDOS attacks, tools and DDOS defense mechanisms," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Application*, Vol. 1, issue 3, pp. 438-440, 2011.
- [3] D. Moore, C. Shannon, D. Brown, G. Voelker and S. Savage, "Inferring Internet denial-of-service activity," *ACM Transactions on Computer Systems*, Vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 115-139, 2006.
- [4] J. Mirkovic and P. Reiher, "A taxonomy of DDoS attack and DDoS defense mechanisms," *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Rev*, Vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 39-53, 2004.
- [5] https://security.radware.com/uploadedFiles/Resources_and_Content/Attack_Tools/CyberSecurityontheOffense.pdf (accessed on 05,09,2017).
- [6] M. Dorigo and L.M. Gambardella, "Ant Colony System: A co-operative learning approach to travelling salesman problem," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computing*, Vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 53-66, 1997.
- [7] V. Aghaei-Foroushani and A. Heywood, "Probabilistic Flow Marking for IP Traceback (PFM)," *IEEE Transaction on Computers*, pp. 229-236, 2015.
- [8] J. Liu, Z. Lee, and Y. Chung, "Dynamic Probabilistic packet marking for efficient IP traceback," *Elsevier Journal of Computer Networks*, Vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 866-882, 2007.
- [9] S. Yu, W. Zhou, S. Guo and M. Guo, "A Feasible IP Traceback Framework through Dynamic Deterministic Packet Marking," *IEEE Transaction on Computers*, Vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 1418-1427, 2016.
- [10] S. Saurabh and A. Sairam, "ICMP based IP traceback with negligible overhead for highly distributed reflector attack using bloom filters," *Elsevier Journal of Computer Communications*, Vol. 42, pp. 60-69, 2014.
- [11] H. Aljifri, M. Smets and A. Pons, "IP traceback using header compression," *Elsevier Journal of Computers and Security*, Vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 136-151, 2003.
- [12] F. Yan, H. Zhu, C. Shuang and Y. Xin-Chun, "A lightweight IP traceback scheme depending on TTL," *Elsevier Journal of Procedia engineering*, Vol. 29, pp. 1932-1937, 2012.
- [13] G. Lai, C. Chen, B. Jeng and W. Chao, "Ant-based IP Traceback," *Elsevier Journal of Expert Systems with Applications*, Vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 3071-3080, 2008.
- [14] M. Hamed-Hamzehkolaie, R. Sanei, C. Chen, X. Tian and M. Nezhad, "Bee-based IP Traceback," *IEEE International Conference on fuzzy systems and knowledge discovery*, pp. 968-972, 2014.
- [15] P. Wang, H. Lin and T. Wang, "An improved Ant colony system algorithm for solving IP traceback problem," *Elsevier Journal of Information Sciences*, Vol. 326, pp. 172-187, 2016.
- [16] J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "A new optimizer using particles swarm theory," in *Proceedings of Sixth International Symposium on Micro machine and Human science*, IEEE Service Center, Piscataway, pp. 39-43, 1995.
- [17] R. Kuo, S. Hong and Y. Huang, "Integration of particle swarm optimization-based fuzzy neural network and artificial neural network for supplier selection," *Journal of Applied Math Model*, Vol. 34, pp. 3976-90, 2010.